

Supplemental Table S1: information about the farms participated in the study. All animals in the study were Israeli Holstein–Friesian cows.

Farm	Geographic location¹	n²	Parity³	Annual milk yield (kg)⁴
Nahshonim	Central Israel (32°06'N, 34°95'E)	98	2.44±0.15 (1-6)	11,492
Be'erot Yitshak	Central Israel (32°02'N, 34°54'E)	146	2.47±0.13 (1-9)	12,539
Zikim	Southern Israel (31°61'N, 34°52'E)	59	2.42±0.18 (1-5)	12,486
Gvar'am	Southern Israel (31°59'N, 34°61'E)	60	2.25±0.21 (1-10)	12,396
Dorot	Southern Israel (31°50'N, 34°65'E)	52	2.65±0.21 (1-6)	12,925

¹Farms locations are presented as area (latitude, longitude)

²Number of cows included from each farm

³Mean±SEM (range)

⁴Mean annual milk yield per cow

Supplemental Table S2: voluntary waiting periods in the farms participated in the study by calendar months.

Voluntary waiting period (DIM¹)										
Farm	Nahshonim		Be'erot Yitshak		Zikim		Gvar'am		Dorot	
Month	Primi ²	Multi ³								
January	100	100	80	70	110	110	150	120	100	100
February	100	100	130	120	110	110	150	120	100	100
Mars	100	100	130	120	100	100	150	120	95	95
April	70	60	130	120	80	80	150	120	80	75
May	70	60	130	120	80	80	90	80	75	70
June	70	60	130	120	80	80	90	80	70	60
July	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	70	60
August	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	70	65
September	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	75	70
October	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	80	80
November	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	90	90
December	70	60	80	70	80	80	90	80	100	100

¹ Days in milk

² Primiparous cows

³ Multiparous cows

Supplemental Table S3: Periparturient diseases. The prevalence of ketosis, metritis, retained fetal membranes, as well as body condition score (at 40-60DIM) are presented for all cows in the study. Cows were defined as CEM positive by PMN% threshold of $\geq 4\%$ at 35 ± 5 DIM (E35), and at 65 ± 5 DIM (E65). Differences between CEM positive (CEM+) and CEM negative (CEM-) cows were analyzed by Chi-square test.

	All cows E35				All cows E65			
	All	CEM +	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value	All	CEM+	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value
Ketosis	36.1% (140/388)	40.7% (57/140)	33.5% (83/248)	0.1877	35.8% (135/377)	39.4% (41/104)	34.4% (94/273)	0.4335
Metritis	46.6% (180/386)	55.0% (77/140)	41.9% (103/246)	0.0173	45.6% (171/375)	55.3% (57/103)	41.9% (114/272)	0.0268
RFM¹	3.6% (14/386)	2.9% (4/140)	4.1% (10/246)	0.7436	3.7% (14/375)	5.8% (6/103)	2.9% (8/272)	0.3126
BCS²								
<2.5	11.4% (43/376)	14.1% (19/135)	10.0% (24/241)	0.3129	11.5% (42/366)	13% (13/100)	10.9% (29/266)	0.6849
2.5-3.5	87.0% (327/376)	85.2% (115/135)	88.0% (212/241)		87.2% (319/366)	85.0% (85/100)	88.0% (234/266)	
>3.5	1.6% (6/376)	0.7% (1/135)	2.1% (5/241)		1.4% (5/366)	2.0% (2/100)	1.1% (3/266)	

¹ Retained fetal membranes

² Body condition score

Supplemental Table S4: Periparturient diseases in primiparous and multiparous cows. The prevalence of ketosis, metritis, retained fetal membranes (RFM), as well as body condition score (at 40-60DIM) are presented for primiparous (left) and multiparous (right) cows independently. Primiparous cows were defined as CEM positive by PMN% threshold of $\geq 7\%$ at 35 ± 5 DIM (E35); multiparous cows defined as CEM positive by PMN% threshold of $\geq 4\%$ at 65 ± 5 DIM (E65). Differences between CEM positive (CEM+) and CEM negative (CEM-) cows were analyzed by Chi-square test.

	Primiparous cows (E35)				Multiparous cows (E65)			
	All	CEM+	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value	All	CEM+	CEM-	χ^2 -test P value
Ketosis	33.1% (44/133)	45.9% (17/37)	28.1% (27/96)	0.0798	38% (92/242)	44.9% (31/69)	35.3% (61/173)	0.2106
Metritis	49.6% (66/133)	64.9% (24/37)	43.8% (42/96)	0.0467	45.4% (109/240)	57.4% (39/68)	40.7% (70/172)	0.0284
RFM¹	1.5% (2/133)	0% (0/37)	2.1% (2/96)	0.9286	5% (12/240)	7.4% (5/68)	4.1% (7/172)	0.4697
BCS²								
<2.5	6.9% (9/130)	2.8% (1/36)	8.5% (8/94)	0.2708	14.6% (34/233)	18.2% (12/66)	13.2% (22/167)	0.4790
2.5-3.5	90.8% (118/130)	97.2% (35/36)	88.3% (83/94)		84.5% (197/233)	80.3% (53/66)	86.2% (144/167)	
>3.5	2.3% (3/130)	0% (0/36)	3.2% (3/94)		0.9% (2/233)	1.5% (1/66)	0.6% (1/167)	

¹ Retained fetal membranes

² Body condition score

Supplemental Table S5: *P* values resulted from 1st AI conception rate univariable analyses for potential confounders (Chi-square test). If the *P* value resulted from the univariable test was ≤ 0.2 (bolded), the factor was included as confounder in the statistical model analyzed 1st AI conception rate in CEM positive vs. negative cows; the effects of the farm and the voluntary waiting period were forced into the models.

Variable	All cows <i>P</i> value	Primiparous cows <i>P</i> value	Multiparous cows <i>P</i> value
BCS ¹	0.9695	0.5519	0.6428
Ketosis	0.2060	0.2175	0.7292
VWP ²	0.2706	0.6573	0.1104
Parity ³	0.0141	--	--
Metritis	0.7860	0.8313	0.8907
RFM ⁴	0.4215	0.7652	0.8619

¹ Body condition score at 40-60DIM

² Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

³ Parity, either primiparous or multiparous

⁴ Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

⁵ Retained fetal membranes

Supplemental Table S6: *P* values resulted from 180DIM pregnancy rate univariable analyses for potential confounders (Chi-square test). If the *P* value resulted from the univariable test was ≤ 0.2 (bolded), the factor was included as confounder in the statistical model analyzed 180DIM pregnancy rate in CEM positive vs. negative cows; the effects of the farm and the voluntary waiting period were forced into the models.

Variable	All cows <i>P</i> value	Primiparous cows <i>P</i> value	Multiparous cows <i>P</i> value
BCS ¹	0.0908	0.1869	0.2749
Ketosis	0.1546	0.1644	0.4995
VWP ²	0.0686	0.3383	0.1676
Parity ³	0.9037	--	--
Metritis	0.2165	0.6117	0.3459
RFM ⁴	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000

¹ Body condition score at 40-60DIM

² Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

³ Parity, either primiparous or multiparous

⁴ Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

⁵ Retained fetal membranes

Supplemental Table S7: *P* values resulted from open days univariable analyses for potential confounders (Log-rank test). If the *P* value resulted from the univariable test was ≤ 0.2 (bolded), the factor was included as confounder in the statistical model analyzed open days in CEM positive vs. negative cows; the effects of the farm and the voluntary waiting period were forced into the models.

Variable	All cows <i>P</i> value	Primiparous cows <i>P</i> value	Multiparous cows <i>P</i> value
BCS ¹	0.3550	0.9590	0.2370
Ketosis	0.2410	0.0100	0.5790
VWP ²	0.0733	0.0366	0.0280
Parity ³	0.5690	--	--
Metritis	0.1940	0.0600	0.8900
RFM ⁴	0.7530	0.3900	0.9010

¹ Body condition score at 40-60DIM

² Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

³ Parity, either primiparous or multiparous

⁴ Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

⁵ Retained fetal membranes

Supplemental Table S8: *P* values resulted from time to first insemination univariable analyses for potential confounders (Log-rank test). If the *P* value resulted from the univariable test was ≤ 0.2 (bolded), the factor was included as confounder in the statistical model analyzed time to first insemination in CEM positive vs. negative cows; the effects of the farm and the voluntary waiting period were forced into the models.

Variable	All cows <i>P</i> value	Primiparous cows <i>P</i> value	Multiparous cows <i>P</i> value
BCS ¹	0.4230	0.1360	0.3210
Ketosis	0.1470	0.0870	0.6060
VWP ²	0.0400	0.2610	0.0680
Parity ³	0.6860	--	--
Metritis	0.2220	0.3660	0.4070
RFM ⁴	0.7900	0.7350	0.8640

¹ Body condition score at 40-60DIM

² Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

³ Parity, either primiparous or multiparous

⁴ Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

⁵ Retained fetal membranes

Supplemental Table S9: *P* values resulted from waste days univariable analyses for potential confounders (Log-rank test). If the *P* value resulted from the univariable test was ≤ 0.2 (bolded), the factor was included as confounder in the statistical model analyzed waste days in CEM positive vs. negative cows; the effects of the farm and the voluntary waiting period were forced into the models.

Variable	All cows <i>P</i> value	Primiparous cows <i>P</i> value	Multiparous cows <i>P</i> value
BCS ¹	0.7090	0.3110	0.5710
Ketosis	0.1580	0.3880	0.2700
VWP ²	0.0183	0.3070	0.0183
Parity ³	0.2280	--	--
Metritis	0.4200	0.9500	0.2830
RFM ⁴	0.8780	0.9330	0.8530

¹ Body condition score at 40-60DIM

² Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

³ Parity, either primiparous or multiparous

⁴ Voluntary waiting period (DIM)

⁵ Retained fetal membranes